

TEMPERATURE AND LOADING RATE EFFECTS ON
THE SHEAR STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL
PULTRUDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The results of the effects of the test temperature and the loading rate on the shear strength of unidirectional pultruded glass-fiber reinforced epoxy (GFRE) and glass-fiber reinforced polyester (GFRP) are reported. Six temperatures ranging from -15°C to 100°C and five loading rates ranging from 1 mm/min to 18000 mm/min were used.

At a given test temperature and for loading rates ranging between 1 to 1000 mm/min, the shear strength (τ_u) increases linearly with the logarithm of the loading rate. This behavior is consistent with Eyring plots reported for unreinforced polymers suggesting that there is a unique flow mechanism controlling the loading rate. On the other hand, it was noticed that the shear strength reaches a maximum value at 1000 mm/min and then starts to decrease. This decrease is found to be more pronounced at low temperatures and corresponds to the occurrence of multiple fracture mechanisms.

The shear strength versus temperature curves consist in two linear portions. The transition between the two linear portions is believed to correspond to a change of the fracture mechanisms from matrix dominated at low temperatures to fiber/matrix interface dominated at high temperatures. Such a statement is confirmed by fracture surface observations.

KEYWORDS : TEMPERATURE, LOADING RATE, SHEAR, COMPOSITES
FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACE.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical design parameters for unidirectional pultruded composite beams is their shear strength. In general, the shear behavior of unidirectional composites is governed by the properties of the matrix and the fiber/matrix interface. Due to the viscoelastic nature of the matrix, the shear strength of the composite is expected to be affected by the temperature and the loading rate.

A large amount of literature was dedicated to the effect of the loading rate and temperature on the mechanical properties of unreinforced polymers. The most known modelization technique is that which is based on Eyring's model of the flow of solids which correlates the effects of temperature and strain rate on flow stress (1). The experimental results of measurements of the yield stress σ_y at varying strain rates are usually rearranged in the form of equation (1) (1):

$$\frac{\sigma_y}{T} = \left(\frac{2}{V^*} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\Delta H}{T} \right) + 2.303 R \text{Log} \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_y}{\dot{\epsilon}_0} \right] \quad (1)$$

where T is the test temperature, V^* the activation volume, ΔH the activation enthalpy, $\dot{\epsilon}_y$ the imposed strain rate at yield and $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ a constant. In the cases where the strain rate is controlled by a unique flow mechanism, the Eyring plot of σ_y/T against $\log \dot{\epsilon}$ will give straight lines.

Contrary to that of unreinforced plastics, the analysis of the effect of the temperature and the loading rate in composite materials is more complex because of the large number of deformations and fracture mechanisms involved. In the particular case of the shear strength, the governing fracture mechanisms are the matrix and the fiber/matrix interface. Despite the numerous investigations dealing with this subject (2-6), the balance between these two mechanisms, particularly when the temperature and the loading rate are varied, is not yet clear. Han and Koutsky (5) suggest that in the case of GFRP, the interface bound between the matrix and the fibers is enhanced at low temperatures due to the shrinkage of the matrix around the fiber upon cooling. Law et al (6) report that for a commercial fiber glass reinforced composite the interlaminar fracture energy increased with decreased temperatures. Supported by fractographic observations, this behavior was explained by the fact that the fracture is adhesive at room temperature and cohesive at low temperatures. This investigation is an attempt toward the

understanding of the effect of the temperature and the loading rate on the shear strength and the fracture mechanisms of pultruded composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 The materials and the specimens Two unidirectional pultruded composite materials were used in this study: a glass fiber-reinforced polyester (GFRP) and a glass fiber-reinforced epoxy (GFRE). In each case, the glass content was 80% in weight and the materials were in the form of half-round rods of 6.7 mm radius (r). The short beam shear specimens were tested at a span-to-depth ratio of 5.

A three point bending fixture was designed to allow the testing of the half-round specimens. The specimens were loaded at the mid-span of the flat surface with the round surface down. The support anvils were similar to those required by the ASTM standard D4475-85.

The maximum shear stress τ_{\max} prevailing at the neutral plane was calculated using the beam theory, and for the case of half-round rods, it is given by:

$$\tau_{\max} = 0.446 P_{\max} / r^2 \quad (2)$$

where P_{\max} is the maximum load, and r the specimen radius.

2.2 The Three Point Bending Test The tests were performed on a servohydraulic MTS fatigue machine equipped with a temperature cabinet. The load displacement curves were recorded using a data acquisition system linked to an IBM PC on which all the necessary computations were made.

The use of a fatigue machine was particularly useful for this investigation for two reasons:

- 1) It allows an instantaneous unloading of the specimen at any load or displacement for any loading rate. Particularly, a test can be run so that the specimen is unloaded as soon as the displacement at the maximum load is reached. This will allow a precise determination of the fracture mechanism corresponding to the maximum load.
- 2) It permits the reaching of a constant loading rate as high as 20000 mm/min, which is almost a low rate impact.

Finally, a JEOL 820 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was used for fracture surface observations.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of the Loading Rate on the Shear Strength The effect of the loading rate on the apparent shear strength τ_u at different test temperatures is shown in figure 1a for GFRE and figure 1b for GFRP, and the following observations can be made.

- a) At a given temperature, and for loading rates ranging between 1 and 1000 mm/min, the shear strength τ_u increases linearly with the logarithm of the loading rate. In this loading rate range, the slope of $\tau_u - \log \dot{\epsilon}$ curve, which expresses the loading rate sensitivity of τ_u , seems to be temperature independent.
- b) The shear strength reaches a maximum value at 1000 mm/min and then starts to decrease slightly. This effect is attenuated at high temperatures, particularly for GFRP.

The plots of $\tau_u - \log \dot{\epsilon}$ at different temperatures are consistent with Eyring plots reported for unreinforced polymers (1). However, the linearity of the $\tau_u - \log \dot{\epsilon}$ curves is to be expected only when there is a unique flow mechanism controlling the strain rate. Since the major material elements which are expected to govern the shear fracture are the matrix and the fiber/matrix interface, an implication of the linearity of the $\tau_u - \log \dot{\epsilon}$ curves is that the same material element (the matrix or the fiber/matrix) controls the fracture when the loading rate increases. In other words, if the fracture is matrix controlled at low loading rates it will continue to be so at high loading rates as long as the linearity is preserved.

Another noticeable point from the plots of figure 1 is the decrease of the shear strength when the loading rate is increased above 10^3 mm/min. Additional tests in the loading rate range 10^3 mm/min to 3 m/s (impact rate) at room temperature confirms this trend (7). More precisely, it was found that the shear strength starts to decrease at 5000 mm/min and then stabilizes. The shear planes are found to be more irregular and at impact rates, the fractured specimens show a multiple cracking pattern rather than regular shear planes as at loading rates below 5000 mm/min. This behavior is explained by the fact that at high loading rates the matrix responds as a brittle material.

A brittle material is more sensitive adventitious processing defects such as microcracks and microvoids which act as stress concentration sites and lower the strength. This assumption seems to be consistent with the fact that the relative decrease of τ_u at high loading rates tends to attenuate when the temperature increases. At high temperature the matrix exhibits a more ductile behavior which lowers the stress concentration.

3.2 Effect of the Test Temperature on the Shear Strength The effect of the test temperature on the shear strength τ_u for different loading rates is shown in figure 2 for GFRE, a similar general pattern behaviour was found for GFRP, and the following observations can be made.

- a) At a given loading rate, the τ_u versus T curves can be approximated by two linear portions. The first linear portion describes the behavior at low temperatures and the second portion, which has a larger slope, describes the behavior at high temperatures.
- b) By considering that within a temperature range (high or low), the slope of the τ_u - T curves expresses the temperature sensitivity of the shear strength, it can be concluded that the temperature sensitivity of τ_u is rate independant. In other words, the ratio by which the shear strength will be reduced when the temperature is increased from a temperature T_1 to a temperature T_2 can be evaluated at any constant loading rate.

The decrease of the shear strength when the temperature is increased can be related to two factors: first, the viscoelastic behaviour of the polymeric matrix which affects both the modulus and ultimate strength and secondly to the properties of the interphase between the fibers and the matrix.

The viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix is well reflected by the shape of the load-displacement (P- δ) curves as shown in figure 3 for a loading rate of 10 mm/min. From the P- δ curves observed in figure 3, it is evident that increasing the test temperature causes a significant decrease of the slope of the elastic portion, and hence in the shear modulus. On the other hand, if we consider that the end of the linear portion corresponds to the beginning of the yielding in the matrix, it can be seen that the yielding process extends dramatically as the temperature increases. Meanwhile, it is interesting to ask how a sharp drop in the P- δ curve, which is characteristic of an instable crack propagation, interrupts the yielding process. To interpret this behavior, it is suggested that the yielding process and the

final fracture are not related to the same material element. The yielding process is related to the matrix while the final fracture is related to the fiber/matrix interface. Such an assumption applies better to high temperatures since at low temperatures the yielding is very limited. However, the most efficient method to investigate the fracture mechanisms is by direct observation of the fracture surfaces.

Before the fracture surfaces analysis is made, it is also interesting to mention that the change in the slope of the $\tau_u - T$ curve is similar to that reported in the literature for some unreinforced plastics (8). In the case of these materials the low temperature branch corresponds to a brittle fracture, the high temperature branch corresponds to a ductile fracture and the junction between the two branches is a kind of a ductile/ brittle transition. In the present case, even though it is certain that the change in the slope of the $\tau_u - T$ curve corresponds to a major change in the fracture mechanisms, this does not necessarily mean that this change is the result of the occurrence of a ductile/brittle transition. In fact, it is believed that this change in the slope of $\tau_u - T$ curves corresponds to a change in the fracture mechanism from a matrix dominated fracture at low temperature to a matrix/fiber interface dominated fracture at high temperatures.

This assumption is clearly confirmed by the SEM observations of the fracture surfaces shown in figures 4a and b respectively at -15°C and 75°C for GFRE. As it can be seen on figure 4a, at high temperature, the surface of the fibers seems to be clean indicating that the crack propagation proceeds at the fiber/matrix interface. At low temperature (figure 4b), substantial amount of resin still remain bound to the fiber. Similar observations were reported recently by Lau et al. (6) in an investigation dealing with the fracture behavior of a glass-fiber reinforced polyester at room temperature and 77 K. However, reference (6) do not give any indication as to why the exposed glass fibers at 77 K are not clean but rather contain considerable amounts of adhered matrix while at room temperature the fibers are relatively matrix free. Obviously, a rational interpretation of the change in the fracture mode from matrix dominated to interface dominated be achieved without a good knowledge of the molecular structure at the interface and only speculative explanations could be given. Two possibilities are proposed.

The first one is based on the fact that the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between the fiber and the matrix induces shear stresses and strains at the interface. Consequently, when the load is applied

to the material, the interfaces reach its ultimate strength before the matrix does.

The second interpretation is based on the fact that the material which constitutes the interphase region may have a glass transition (T_g) significantly lower than that of the matrix. Indeed, as reported recently by Thomason and Morsink (9), the T_g of the coatings used in commercial E-glass fiber varies between -30 and 65°C.

Finally, one should take into account, the fact that at low temperatures the matrix behave as a brittle material in which the processing defects will play an important role in cracks initiation and propagation.

4. CONCLUSION

The aim of this investigation was to determine how the shear strength (τ_u) and the shear fracture mechanisms of two commercial pultruded unidirectional composite rods varies with the test temperature and the loading rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$). By presenting the results in the form $\tau_u - \text{Log}(\dot{\epsilon})$ an attempt if made to examine the applicability of the Eyring model which is based on activated rate process theory. The results suggest that this possibility exists for loading rates ranging between 1 and 1000 mm/min. Above this limit complex fracture mechanisms affect the linearity of the $\tau_u - \text{Log}(\dot{\epsilon})$ curves.

The decrease of the shear strength when the test temperature increases is found to be described by two linear portions. The change in the slope of the $\tau_u - T$ curves which at first sight suggest the occurrence of a ductile-brittle transition is believed to correspond to a change in the fracture mechanisms from matrix controlled fracture at low temperature to a fiber/matrix interface controlled fracture at high temperature.

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Figure 1 - Effect of the loading rate on the shear strength of GFRE (a) and GFRP (b).

Figure 2 - Effect of the test temperature on the shear strength of GFRE.

Figure 3 - Typical load-displacement curves at different temperatures (loading rate 10 mm/min).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 - Fracture surfaces in GFRE at -15°C (a) and + 75°C (b).

